

Studies in Copper(II) Chelates: Part III. Mixed Chelates with Tridentate, Dibasic Schiff Bases and o-Phenanthroline/ α , α' -Dipyridyl

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A large number of Copper(II) mixed chelates having a series of tridentate, dibasic schiff bases (LigH₂) and a molecule of o-phenanthroline or α , α' -dipyridyl have been isolated in pure, crystalline form. These are all of the type [Cu (dipy) (Lig)] or [Cu (o-phen) (Lig)], non-electrolytes and provide paramagnetic moment of ~ 1.8 B. M. The absorption spectra in different solvents indicate some shift in the frequency of absorption. The complexes are believed to possess distorted octahedral stereochemistry at least in solution.

Because of their elegantly simple technique of syntheses, schiff bases have received numerous studies as co-ordinating ligands¹⁻⁶. This study, arising out of our recent interest in the syntheses and characterisation of copper (II) mixed chelates⁷, describes our efforts with a number of tridentate, dibasic acid schiff bases. The bis(N-phenylsalicylaldiminato) copper (II) complex has been reported to react with α , α' -dipyridyl providing apparently an adduct⁸. Aside this report, the literature does not record any extensive study of copper (II) mixed chelate systems, having a tridentate schiff base and a bidentate heterocyclic ligand^{8a}.

We selected a number of such tridentate ligands, arising out of the condensation of such aldehydes as salicylaldehyde, 2-hydroxynaphthaldehyde and resorcyaldehyde with such amines, as glycine, α -(DL)-alanine and anthranilic acid. A mole proportion of copper(II) acetate was added to an alcoholic solution of any of the above schiff bases and after the complexation was over, the resulting solution or mixture was treated with α , α' dipyridyl or o-phenanthroline. The resulting mixed chelates have been isolated in pure, crystalline form and in reasonable yield.

The complexes [Cu(Lig)(o-phen)] and [Cu(Lig)(dipy)] are all soluble in alcohol (except resorcyaldehyde- α -(DL)-alaninalto δ -(o-phenanthroline)copper(II) complex), dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO) and pyridine and only sparingly soluble in benzene or chloroform. As expected, the complexes provide non-electrolyte conductance values in methanol (cf. Table I).

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Certain schiff bases, such as N-isopropylsalicylideneamine react with copper(II) providing bis-complexes, which reveals ligand field bands at $\sim 21,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$, $13,500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and at $8,500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ to indicate a distorted tetrahedral structure¹⁰. As against this a quadri-dentate schiff base, ethelenediamine bis (salicyladehyde)⁶, gives rise to a green coloured copper(II) complex with longest wavelength absorption band around $575\text{ m}\mu$ ($17,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$) indicating an enforced cis-planar stereochemistry. The planar bis (n-butyl salicylidena-minato) copper (II)¹⁰ has an absorption band around $16,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$. Viewed in this back-ground, the absorption spectra of several of our complexes in ethanol, dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO) and pyridine are quite interesting. In most cases, the spectra show two absorption bands, the one at near ultraviolet having high extinction co-efficient and resembling the mother schiff base ligands. These are certainly associated with intra-ligand or charge transfer transitions^{6,10}. The second absorption frequency in ethanol in the range $14,000$ — $16,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ makes unequivocal stereochemical assignment difficult. In fact, the frequency range of absorption alone cannot be considered as an unfailing tool to determine the geometry of the complex.¹¹ However, certain remarks seem to be called for. In the absence of diffuse reflectance spectra, we are mainly basing our conclusions on the various solution spectra. Measurements indicate no absorption bands around the expected tetrahedral frequency region¹⁰. This is also not probably to be expected because of the association of a strong field ligand, o-phenanthroline or α , α' -dipyridyl in the complex. On the other hand, all the mixed chelates absorb around a frequency suitably to be called the distorted octahedral region. One recent study of 5-co-ordinated copper(II) complex, namely, 6-methyl 2-picolyamine provides a frequency range in solution around 700 - $750\text{ m}\mu$ ¹². Our syntheses have apparently a co-ordination number of five, as analyses indicate practically no colour change on dehydration of a few hydrated samples. The absorption ranges are also comparable with the above study. Almost all the different mixed complexes show some slight shift in spectra in three solvents namely, ethanol, dimethylsulfoxide and pyridine as is to be expected on the basis of distorted octahedral geometry at least in solution^{13,14,15} (cf. Fig. 1 and Table I). However, the spectral shifts are not in keeping with the positions of the donor solvents in the spectrochemical series. We are therefore constrained to comment that pyridine is less efficiently bound to an already complexed copper(II) than the other two solvents. This reversal of the expected behaviour has also been found in several other copper(II) complexes in our laboratory. This is also to be mentioned that the absorption spectra of the copper(II) complexes of the same schiff base in combination with either α , α' -dipyridyl or o-phenanthroline show little difference among them.

The magnetic moments of all these complexes are within the range of ~ 1.8 B.M. Although in a few cases the moments are slightly higher than spin-only values, these are not as high to support distorted tetrahedral structures. However, this is to be emphasized that magnetic evidence particularly at one room temperature (Table I) cannot be readily used to determine the stereochemistry unequivocally⁶.

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Fig. 1. Solution absorption Spectra of Schiff base α , α' -dipyridyl (or o-phenanthroline) Copper (II) Complexes in different Solvents. [Cu(dipy) (Hynapalan)] in ethanol (curve 1), in DMSO (curve 2) and in pyridine (curve 3). [Cu(o-phen) (Hynapalan)] in ethanol (curve 4), in DMSO (curve 5) and in pyridine (curve 6).

TABLE I

Electronic spectral data, Conductance values and Magnetic moments of the mixed chelates

Complex or Reagent	Solvent	Colour in solution	Absorption spectral bands (cm^{-1})	ϵ_{max}	Conductance in methanol in mhos $\text{cm}^2 \text{mole}^{-1}$ (at 28°C)	μ_{eff} B.M. (at T° Abs.)	
1. [Cu(dipy) (Salan)].0.5 H ₂ O	EtOH	Yellow	(i) 23,810 (ii) 14,490-13,890	5,420 122	—	1.88 B.M. (296°)**	
	DMSO	Yellow	(i) 24,390 (ii) 14,290-13,700	8,880 125			
	py	Greenish-yellow	(i) 24,390 (ii) 14,710-14,080	7,500 132			
	EtOH	Yellow	(i) 24,390 (ii) 23,810	275 200	—	—	
2. [Cu(o-phen) (Salan)]	EtOH	Yellow	(i) 24,390 (ii) 14,490-13,890	5,360 135	4.15	1.86 (296°)	
	DMSO	Yellowish-green	(i) 24,390 (ii) 14,490-14,080	8,380 142.0			
	py	Greenish-yellow	(i) 25,640 (ii) 14,710-14,290	16,450 165.0			
3. [Cu(o-phen) (Salgly)].0.5H ₂ O	EtOH	Yellowish-green	(i) 27,030 (ii) 15,150-14,490	4,620 125	—	1.88 (303°)	
	DMSO	Greenish-yellow	(i) 27,030 (ii) 15,380-14,710	5,500 133			
	py	Green	(i) 27,030-26,320 (ii) 15,620-15,150	5,125 155			

TABLE 1 (Contd.)

Complex or Reagent	Solvent	Colour in solution	Absorption spectral bands (cm ⁻¹)	ε max	Conductance in methanol in mhos cm ² mole ⁻¹ (at 28°C)	μ _{eff} B.M (at T° Abs.)
4. [Cu(dipy) (Salgly)]. 4H ₂ O	EtOH	Green	(i) 27,030	5,690	—	1.86 (303°)
			(ii) 15,150-14,490	136		
	DMSO	Green	(i) 27,030	5,740		
			(ii) 15,150-14,490	140		
	py	Green	(i) 27,030-26,320	5,500		
			(ii) 15,620-14,930	163		
5. [Cu(dipy)(Salalan)]. 4H ₂ O	EtOH	Green	(i) 27,030	4,940	—	1.84 (301°)
			(ii) 15,380-14,490	113		
	DMSO	Green	(i) 27,030	5,560		
			(ii) 15,380-14,710	125		
	py	Green	(i) 27,030-26,320	5,750		
			(ii) 15,870-15,150	158		
6. [Cu(o-phen) (Salalan)]. 4.5H ₂ O	EtOH	Green with yellow tinge	(i) 27,030	4,960	5.56	1.90 (300°)
			(ii) 15,150-14,490	110		
	DMSO	Green	(i) 27,030	6,050		
			(ii) 15,380-14,710	135		
	py	Green	(i) 27,030-26,320	5,000		
			(ii) 15,620-15,150	148		
7. [Cu (o-phen) (Hynapan)] .H ₂ O	EtOH	yellow	(i) 23,810	*	—	1.90 (299°)
			(ii) 14,490-13,890	*		
	DMSO	Yellow	(i) 23,260	12,240		
			(ii) 14,710-13,890	162		
	py	Dirty-yellow	(i) 23,810-23,260	11,150		
			(ii) 14,710-14,080	157		
Hynapan	...	(i) 22,730	9,620			
		(ii) 23,810	6,310			
8. [Cu (dipy) (Hynapan)] .3H ₂ O	EtOH	yellow	(i) 24,390-23,810	3,530	5.35	1.88 (302°)
			(ii) 14,710-13,890	100		
	DMSO	Yellow	(i) 23,260	10,620		
			(ii) 14,290-13,700	152.0		
	py	Dirty-yellow	(i) 23,810-23,260	10,770		
			(ii) 14,710-14,080	160		
9. [Cu (dipy) (Hynapgly)] .1.5H ₂ O	EtOH	Yellowish-green	(i) 25,640	6,650	3.66	1.80 (299°)
			(ii) 15,380-14,930	147.0		
	DMSO	Yellowish-green	(i) 25,640	7,100		
			(ii) 15,380-14,710	147.0		
	py	Yellowish-green	(i) 25,640	6,600		
			(ii) 15,870-15,150	165		
10. [Cu (o-phen) Hynapgly)] .1.5H ₂ O	EtOH	Yellowish-green	(i) 25,640	*	—	1.82 (299°)
			(ii) 15,150-14,490	*		
	DMSO	Yellowish-green	(i) 25,640	6,910		
			(ii) 15,380-14,930	147		
	py	Green	(i) 25,640	6,120		
			(ii) 15,870-15,150	167.0		
11. [Cu (o-phen) (Hynapalan)] H ₂ O	EtOH	Green	(i) 25,640	5,680	6.32	1.85 (300°)
			(ii) 15,380-14,710	141		
	DMSO	Yellowish-green	(i) 25,640-25,000	6,870		
			(ii) 15,870-14,930	157.0		
	py	Green	(i) 25,640	6,400		
			(ii) 16,130-15,380	177		

TABLE I (Contd)

Complex or Reagent	Solvent	Colour in solution	Absorption spectral bands (cm ⁻¹)	ϵ max	Conductance in methanol in mhos cm ² mole ⁻¹ (at 28°C)	μ_{eff} B.M. (at T° Abs.)
12. [Cu (dipy) (Hynapalan)] .2H ₂ O	EtOH	Green with yellow tinge	(i) 25,640 (ii) 15,380-14,710	6,600 135	—	1.81 (301°)
	DMSO	Green	(i) 25,640-25,000 (ii) 15,380-14,710	6,120 152		
	py	Yellowish-green	(i) 25,640 (ii) 15,870-15150	8,300 176		
13. [Cu (dipy) (Resan)]. 1.5H ₂ O	EtOH	Straw-yellow	(i) 25,640 (ii) 14,490-13,890	* *	5.79	1.81 (303°)
	DMSO	Greenish-yellow	(i) 25,640 (ii) 14,290-13,700	14,810 146		
	py	Yellow	(i) 25,640 (ii) 14,930-14,080	24,750 155		
14. [Cu (o-phen) (Resan)] .3.5H ₂ O	EtOH	Greenish-yellow	(i) 25,640 (ii) 14,490-13,890	* *	—	1.85 (301°)
	DMSO	Yellow	(i) 25,640 (ii) 14,710-14,080	15,190 167		
	py	Yellow	(i) 25,640 (ii) 14,710-14,290	16,450 165		
15. [Cu(o-phen)(Resgly)] .2H ₂ O	EtOH	Green	(i) 28,570 (ii) 15,380-14,490	* *	5.79	1.80 (303°)
	DMSO	Yellowish-green	(i) 28,570-27,780 (ii) 15,380-14,710	6,900 132		
	py	Yellowish-green	(i) 27,780 (ii) 15,870-15,150	7,670 152		
16. [Cu(dipy) (Resgly)]. 2.5H ₂ O	EtOH	Green	(i) 28,570 (ii) 15,150-14,490	7,500 117	—	1.85 (301°)
	DMSO	Green	(i) 28,570-27,780 (ii) 15,380-14,710	7,810 127		
	py	Green	(i) 27,780 (ii) 15,620-15,150	7,620 150		
17. [Cu(dipy) (Resalan)]. 3H ₂ O	EtOH	Green	(i) 28,570 (ii) 15,380-14,710	8,500 120	6.35	1.83 (303°)
	DMSO	Green	(i) 28,570-27,780 (ii) 15,380-14,710	7,620 124		
	py	Green	(i) 27,780 (ii) 15,620-15,150	8,190 157		
18. [Cu (o-phen) (Resalan)]	DMSO	Green	(i) 27,780 (ii) 15,380-14,930	7,940 143	—	1.86 (300°)
	py	Green	(i) 27,780 (ii) 15,620-15,150	8,880 161		

SalaH₂ = Salicylaldehydianthranilic acid schiff base, SalalanH₂ = Salicylaldehydialanine schiff base, SalglyH₂ = Salicylaldehydiglycine schiff base, HynapanH₂ = 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehydianthranilic acid schiff base, HynapalanH₂ = 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehydialanine schiff base, HynapglyH₂ = 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehydiglycine schiff base, ResanH₂ = resorcydaldehydianthranilic acid schiff base, ResalanH₂ = resorcydaldehydialanine schiff base, ResglyH₂ = resorcydaldehydiglycine, dipv = α , α' -dipyridyl, o-phen = o-phenanthroline, DMSO = dimethylsulfoxide and py = pyridine.

*The optical density measurements were made in saturated solutions. Due to some uncertainty, the molar extinction co-efficients are not presented in the above table.

**Figures in parentheses indicate the absolute temperature at which measurements were made. μ_{eff} was calculated from the relation $\mu_{\text{eff}} = 2.84_{\text{m}} (\chi_{\text{M}} \text{ corr. XT})^{\frac{1}{2}}$ B. M.

EXPERIMENTAL

General Method of Preparation of Complexes :

Salicylaldehydianthranilato(α , α' -*dipyridyl*)*copper*(II) :

Method A : The schiff base (Salicylaldehydianthranilic acid) (0.240 g) dissolved in hot alcohol (about 5 ml.) was treated with an alcoholic solution of cupric acetate (0.2 g in 3-4 ml.) and was refluxed for an hour on steam bath, when a yellow precipitate formed. This was then treated with an alcoholic solution of α , α' -dipyridyl (0.15 g in 2 ml.) and the mixture was further refluxed for 2-3 hr, when the precipitate slowly passed into a clear dirty yellow solution. This solution was then filtered hot and the excess solvent was distilled off to a volume of 3-4 ml. and the solution allowed to cool in the refrigerator over night to yield shining olive green crystals. These were filtered and purified by recrystallisation from hot ethanol and dried in air. Preparation of similar complexes are given in Table II.

Hydroxynaphthaldehydialaninato(α , α' -*dipyridyl*)*copper* (II) :

Method B : An alcoholic solution of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde (0.18 g in 2-3 ml.) was treated with an aqueous solution of α -(DL)-alanine (0.09 g in 1 ml.) and the mixture was refluxed for an hour on the steam bath. To the resulting solution of the schiff base an alcoholic solution of copper(II) acetate (0.2 g in 3-4 ml.) was added and the above described procedure followed. The cold concentrated ethanolic solution (\sim 2 ml.) was then treated with a few ml. of water and cooled in the refrigerator over night when shining, crystalline material separated. These were usually recrystallised from hot aqueous ethanol, filtered and dried in air. Details of syntheses of other parallel complexes appear in Table II.

TABLE II

Characterization data for the mixed chelates

Schiff Base	Method of preparation	Hetero-cyclic Base	Colour	Formula	Analysis		
					%Cu	%N	%H ₂ O
1. Salicylaldehydianthranilic Acid	A	dipy	Olive green	[Cu(dipy) (Lig)]. 0.5 H ₂ O	Found : 13.48 Reqd. : 13.57	8.90 8.98	2.10 1.92
2. -do-	A	o-phen	Olive green	[Cu(o-phen) (Lig)]	Found : 13.08 Reqd. : 13.14	8.72 8.69	— —
3. Salicylaldehydiglycine	B	o-phen	Green	[Cu (o-phen) (Lig)] 0.5 H ₂ O	Found : 14.65 Reqd. : 14.72	9.80 9.73	1.86 2.00
4. -do-	B	dipy	Green	[Cu(dipy) (Lig)]. 4 H ₂ O	Found : 13.51 Reqd. 13.56	10.50 10.59	15.00 15.37
5. Salicylaldehydi- - α -(DL)-alanine	B	dipy	Green	[Cu(dipy)(Lig)]. 4 H ₂ O	Found : 13.08 Reqd. 13.13	8.75 8.70	14.56 14.58
6. -do-	B	o-phen	Shining bright green	[Cu(o-phen) (Lig)]. 4.5 H ₂ O	Found : 12.26 Reqd. : 12.32	8.21 8.14	15.81 15.85
7. 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehydi-anthranilic Acid.	A	o-phen	Yellow	[Cu (o-phen (Lig)]. H ₂ O	Found : 11.41 Reqd. : 11.49	7.68 7.60	3.40 3.25
8. -do-	A	dipy	Shining cinnamon colour	[Cu(dipy) (Lig)]. 3 H ₂ O	Found : 11.12 Reqd. : 11.27	7.51 7.46	9.59 9.58
9. 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehydiglycine	A	dipy	Green	[Cu(dipy) (Lig)]. 1.5 H ₂ O	Found : 13.32 Reqd. : 13.41	8.81 8.86	5.40 5.69

TABLE II (Contd.)

Schiff Base	Method of preparation	Hetero-cyclic Base	Colour	Formula	Analysis		
					%Cu	%N	%H ₂ O
10. -do-	A	o-phen	Light green	[Cu(o-phen) (Lig)]. 1.5 H ₂ O	Found : 12.68 Reqd. : 12.76	8.39 8.43	5.33 5.42
11. 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde- α -(DL) alanine	B	o-phen	Shining bright green	[Cu(o-phen) (Lig)]. H ₂ O	Found : 12.61 Reqd. : 12.64	8.50 8.55	3.61 3.50
12. -do-	B	dipy	Green	[Cu(dipy) (Lig)]. 2 H ₂ O	Found : 12.73 Reqd. : 12.79	8.40 8.43	6.88 7.25
13. Resorcyaldehyde-dianthranilic Acid	A	dipy	Olive green	[Cu(dipy) Lig] 1.5 H ₂ O	Found : 12.71 Reqd. : 12.67	8.31 8.37	5.24 5.38
14. -do-	A	o-phen	Olive green	[Cu(o-phen) (Lig)]. 3.5 H ₂ O	Found : 11.28 Reqd. : 11.31	7.52 7.47	10.98 11.21
15. Resorcyaldehydi-glycine	A	o-phen	Dirty green	[Cu(o-phen) (Lig)]. 2 H ₂ O	Found : 13.39 Reqd. : 13.44	8.72 8.87	7.10 7.61
16. -do-	A	dipy	Green	[Cu (dipy) (Lig)] 2.5 H ₂ O	Found : 13.76 Reqd. : 13.88	9.01 9.18	10.00 9.83
17. Resorcyaldehydi- α -(DL)-alanine	B	dipy	Shining deep green	[Cu (dipy) (Lig)]. 3 H ₂ O	Found : 13.20 Reqd. : 13.22	8.80 8.74	11.34 11.24
18. -do-	A	o-phen	Shining dark green	[Cu(o-phen) (Lig)]	Found : 13.94 Reqd. : 14.07	9.32 9.28	— —

Lig H₂=Molecule of the dibasic, tridentate schiff basel ligand. dipy = α , α' -Dipyridyl; o-phen=1,10-Phenanthroline.

Analytical Procedure : Copper was first precipitated as CuS with H₂S. This precipitate was then dissolved in nitric acid-sulphuric acid mixture and was estimated iodometrically. In some cases, copper was also estimated by KHSO₄-fusion technique.

Nitrogen was estimated by Combustion technique.

The magnetic susceptibility measurements of the complexes at room temperature were made by a Gouy's Balance with field strength 8.366×10^3 gauss using G. R. grade copper(II) sulphate pentahydrate as a standard. Diamagnetic corrections were taken from Selwood¹⁶.

Conductivities in methanol were measured by Philips conductivity bridge type PR 9500.

The absorption spectra of the complexes in ethanol, pyridine and DMSO were measured at 8×10^{-5} M concentration over the range of 330 to 500 m μ and at 2×10^{-3} M concentration over the range of 450 to 1000 m μ in a Hilger & Watts UVI spek spectrophotometer. The glass cell with 1 cm light path was used.

One of the authors (D.D.) is thankful to U.G.C., New Delhi, for the award of Research Scholarship.